

Database	Title	Author	Year	Target population	Goals and students' role	Methodology (instruments, models and procedures used)	Engagement assessment (when suitable)	Results and conclusions
Scopus	Sidefect GamePlan: Development of an alcohol and other drug serious game for high school students using a systematic and iterative user-centred game development framework.	Nicholas, J. et al.	2023	High school students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To describe the process behind the development of an online AOD (alcohol and other drugs) serious game to be used by Australian Secondary Education teachers in classes from years 9-10. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of a seven-step systematic and iterative user-centred development framework adapted from Edwards (2008). Such model abides by principles of co-design, gamification, behaviour change, identification of causal pathways and user testing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus groups comprising 36 high school students with a focus on student engagement and learning outcomes deriving from aesthetic, diegetic, content-related and mechanic elements. User tests comprised of scales. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User centred gaming experiences favour student engagement. This construct constitutes a key factor in building effective AOD educational programs. The relatability of the video game characters, together with the relevance of its narratives, contribute to an increase in AOD refusal self-efficacy among other positive behavioural changes. Still, more studies need to be conducted regarding the impact of engagement on AOD learning and behavioural outcomes. The main obstacles to implementing successful AOD educational programs include lack of resources, access to updated information and teacher confidence. It is important to supplement gameplay with different didactic materials and integrate it into interactive teaching strategies, by taking advantage of the gaming experience so as to promote subsequent classroom discussions.

	Serious games for health promotion in adolescents – a systematic scoping review	Andrew, L. et al.	2023	Adolescents.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present a systematic scoping review of serious games used for health promotion with adolescents, aiming at identifying serious games, reviewing the methods used to evaluate them, and the evidence available concerning the impact of educational video games on learning outcomes. When assessed, player engagement was outlined. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Systematic scoping review conducted by a team of researchers, using eligibility criteria and search terms. The protocol used has not been published before. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement assessment occurred through observation of students' level of discussion in the serious video games they played, their rate of competitiveness and interest in responding correctly to the questions. Another method implied measuring "consistency, active participation, confidence, fun, excitement, individual attention, clarity of learning, meaningful work, rigorous thinking, and performance orientation" (Hussein et al., 2019). Asking students whether they would recommend the video game they played and about their willingness to play it again was also used as an engagement assessment method. Finally, the article reports two quantitative methods: the use of a 10-point 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There has been found reasonably solid evidence concerning the ability of professionally designed serious video games to promote engagement and meaningful learning. More studies need to be conducted to ascertain serious video games' impact on students' lifestyles and habits in the long term. The assessed serious video games delve in topics pertinent to youth public health. The avatars used succeeded in supporting engagement, as they mirror the gaming experience provided by commercial video games, which are attractive to youngsters. A multidisciplinary design approach must be privileged, since it provides for rigour, thus improving the quality of the intended serious video games. This helps meet the target audience's high standards in regard to gaming and learning through that experience. Aligning the video game goals and content with subjects' curricula and teachers' standards, to personalize and contextualize learning, improves the likelihood of positive outcomes among students. Considering the marginalized groups in the design of serious video games, and incorporating in them positive messages, defiant of self-fulfillment prophecies, favours engagement and behavioral modification.
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							Likert scale, and the analysis of data related to the video game experience: the number of levels completed by the player and retention and completion numbers.	
	Effects of Digital Game-Based Learning on Students' Cyber Wellness Literacy, Learning Motivations, and Engagement	Wang K., et al.	2023	Primary and Secondary Education students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To explore and tackle the issue of Internet addiction by designing and implementing a digital serious game-course in a middle school. The study foci extend to the effects exerted by DGBL (Digital Game-based Learning) on students' cyber wellness literacy, motivation and engagement. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of the ACRS (Attention, Confidence, Relevance, Satisfaction) model and Educational Escape Room (EER) concept in the process of designing the digital serious game. Use of quasi-experimental research method to compare students' cyber wellness literacy, learning motivations, and learning engagement between the experiment students and a control group. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation was measured by administering a five-point Likert scale adapted from Tüzün (2009), with a focus on intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Engagement assessment occurred through administration of a learning engagement questionnaire, adapted from Urecht Work Engagement Scale—student (UWES-S). It consists of 12 items, measured on a five-point scale, relating to Behavioural engagement, cognitive engagement and emotional engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The students who participated in DGBL showed higher levels of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The use of an Educational Escape Room (ERR) is the mostly likely reason behind such evidence. From the perspective of the ACRS model, intrinsic motivation may be the result of the use of fascinating and thought-provoking scenarios, which provide for reflection on students' habits and possible solutions to real-world problems. Emotional engagement is the only variable where participants in the experiment and students from the control group differed. The user-friendly interface of the video game, as well its preoccupation with providing the player with clear navigation stimulated players' engagement and interest in the resource. Other elements reported that favour engagement were leaderboards and the game's storyline.

	Use of Gamification in Primary and Secondary Education: A Systematic Literature Review	Vrcelj et al.	2023	Primary and Secondary Students.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present a systematic review of the literature on relevant research on the use of gamification in primary and secondary schools to provide insights into the field and make recommendations for future research. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of the principles of Systematic literature review (SLR) by Okoli and Schabram (2010). The protocol was established prior to the review. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most studies showed concern with measuring students' level of motivation, engagement and satisfaction when interacting with gamified digital lessons, tools and platforms. A quantitative approach was privileged, with many studies administering questionnaires, pre- and post- tests and conducting game data analysis. Additional qualitative research was found in some articles, with a focus on interviews, analysis of students' electronic diaries and observations. Other studies resorted to establishing comparisons between experimental and control groups, the control groups being the ones in which traditional learning methods were employed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gamification and game design elements are mainly used in Elementary Education for content learning or formatively assessing students. The most popular game design elements include stories, avatars, challenges, leaderboards, points, badges, awards and progress bars. They are commonly used in combination. Gamification tends to have a positive effect on students' level of achievement and motivation. Partial positive results were also observed. Still very few studies analyse the impact of gamification on primary and secondary schools. It is challenging to find papers empirically focussed on primary and secondary education, as most of them consist of narratives on the benefits of gamification, following the "ad hoc method". Gamification may be an easier and more accessible option than digital serious games, allowing for a widespread use in schools of different socioeconomic backgrounds. In terms of recommendations, the authors suggest that more research should be conducted in primary and secondary schools given the insufficient data concerning those contexts, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. To ensure that the results of the study are reliable and empirically validated, it is important to adopt a mixed methods
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							<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concerning the selected population, it includes teachers, students and, to a lesser extent, parents. 	<p>approach, using qualitative and quantitative methods. Design Based Research (DBR), from Wang and Hannafin (2005), with an emphasis on iterative analysis, development and implementation, based on the collaboration between teachers and designers, is a reliable methodological approach for studies on gamification.</p>
	Gaming & Geography (Education): A Model of Reflexive Analysis of Space & Action in Video Games	Morawski & Wolff-Seidel	2023	Students from 9 and 18 years old.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present the results from a research project titled "Gaming & Geography", in an attempt to legitimize assigning video games the role of a medium in the didactic discourse of geography. A model for critically analysing digital space and action in video games emerged from this research project, with an aim to improve rigor in video game use, in the context of geographic education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative approach, complemented by a qualitative analysis: teacher and student surveys and expert interviews. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teachers were surveyed by students on the influence video games exert on their behaviour inside and outside the classroom. Likewise, students were interviewed so as to self-reflect on the importance video games exhibit in terms of learning and behavioural changes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement in reflective thinking during gameplay was identified as a positive trait of video game which spark discussion on relevant topics concerning societal dimensions – economy, geography, sociology... The presence of nature landscapes, which can be explored at the players' own rhythm, in a similar way to popular RPGs such as Legend of Zelda, also improves motivation and engagement in the video game. A risk arising from this is the possibility that students instrumentally interact with nature, with an aim to exploit it and collect resources, which can harm their learning on sustainability and the importance of good environmental practices. Geography-focused games should provide for a more nuanced understanding of human-environment interactions, thus increasing engagement in good practices. Game developers must be provided with the knowledge needed to create video games aligned with educational goals. Goal setting, feedback, and assessment are important aspects to take into consideration when designing a game that intends to generate good learning outcomes and engagement.

								<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educators must cooperate with game developers so as to build on their pedagogy knowledge and ensure the design of video games that effectively foster students' understanding of important curricula's topics. • Promoting engagement through video games in Geography classes depends on teachers' ability to properly contextualize this resource and ensure that the discussions deriving from the game are in line with broader questions in Geography beyond war and conflicts, such as poverty, exclusion and environmental problems. Most games, however, do not cover those topics. • Engagement in task reflection and orientation tasks positively influences students' cognitive abilities, such as problem-solving and critical thinking. Most students do not believe that engagement in a video game relates to their ability to make decisions in real-life settings. The influence of video games may not extend to all spheres in the player's life. • Video games often offer simplistic solutions to problems that, in the real world, tend to have more complex and nuanced moral implications. This may hinder students' engagement in practices that allow them to use the knowledge they acquired through gaming in real-life scenarios.
	Developing an alcohol and other drug serious game for adolescents: considerations for improving student engagement	Nicholas et al.	2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students who are between 13 and 18 years old. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore perceptions about alcohol and other narcotics; identify factors that are promoting serious play on this topic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interviews with students about their perceptions regarding health serious games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The author does not propose methods for assessing engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The video game depicted contributed to student engagement in learning content related to public health. • The authenticity of the characters and contexts represented in the game, along with

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students as gamers. 			<p>the promotion of social interactions between players, is an aspect that favour engagement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The player's freedom of choice and the alignment between the game's challenge level and gamers' profile are aspects to consider when designing serious video games.
	eLuna: A Co-Design Framework for Narrative Digital Game-Based Learning that Support STEAM	Breien, & Wasson	2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic, Secondary and Higher Education students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present a conceptual model – eLuna – based on co-design, which motivates educators to participate, together with programmers, in the multidisciplinary design of narrative DGBL environments. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of a multidisciplinary model based on co-design. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The author does not propose methods for assessing engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narratives provide a good basis for learning sciences. If combined with video games, designed in a multidisciplinary process involving educators and programmers, they become effective means for creating DGBL environments. These can motivate, engage and educate students. For example, the author describes a pedagogical intervention in which students virtually interact with a simulated laboratory, before conducting experiments in a real laboratory. The simulations provided by video games become, by this logic, a playful space for testing and familiarising youngsters with practices and concepts that will be useful to them in real life.
	Students as game creators: easing the game construction process by using a toolkit to game design	Beça et al.	2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Upper secondary and undergraduate students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To introduce the Gamers4Nature Toolkit, a resource that facilitates the design of environmental-related games by youngsters with no experience in game making. Students as game designers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sessions devoted to game narrative design took place, one-day and two-day sessions, long term (one month) and a 72-hour online Game Jam. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaires were administered to assess the impact of Gamers4Nature Toolkit on easing the game narrative design process, with engagement being indirectly one of the parameters measured. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using a toolkit when designing a video game helps students organize their ideas, while favouring the narrative construction process. This, together with its ability to summarize information capture important game making iterations provided for a good experience from students' standpoint. The toolkit offers promising advantages in terms of structuring ideas, brainstorming and increasing students' awareness of what programming entails. As an engaging artifact capable of facilitating the creation of technological resources, it provides for

								<p>learning settings consonant with XXI century demands for high levels of creativity and critical thinking.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The games resulting from this project combine engaging themes and formats ranging from environmental-focused quizzes, role-playing games to runner games aimed at avoiding obstacles and capturing polluting substances. • Preliminary data indicates that teachers – with previous knowledge on gamification and game-based learning, but not used to resorting to it in their practices – found the toolkit helpful for fostering creativity, look at problems from different perspectives and able to engage students in exploring different subjects’ content.
	Gamification in a textbook for Brazilian learners of English	Franco, C.	2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young students and teenagers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To present and discuss the strategies implemented to turn an English course book used by young Brazilians into a gamified one. • Students as video gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporation of game design elements, proposed by Deterding et al. (2011), into a course book. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The author does not propose methods for assessing engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The article describes a gamified version of an English course book, identifying elements from digital game design that enhance engagement – medals, levels, shifts, challenges, and clear goals. • Gamification allows for increasing students’ autonomy, since it is them who make their decisions throughout the learning process, forging their own path.
	A gamificação como design instrucional	Stuart, N.	2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary school students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To present an instructional design for game-centred pedagogical practices. • Student as video gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of motivational models suggested by Kapp (2012) into an instructional design for pedagogical practices centred on video games; these models are used in Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The author does not propose methods for assessing engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student engagement in educational video games is a significant contributor to engaging and efficient learning. • Teachers can turn the classroom into a place similar to multiplayer video game scenarios, in which a didactic sequence mediated by technological elements, such as digital

						classes taught to three high school classes in Brazil).		<p>mini-games, simulations, collaborative challenges and quizzes can take place.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing educational videogames constitutes a complex process, for it should be carried out by a multidisciplinary professional team.
	An Innovative Multi-Layer Gamification Framework for Improved STEM Learning Experience	Zhao et al.	2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High school students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Propose an innovative conceptual model, <i>NEWTON</i>-enhanced gamification model (N-EGM), for the integration of digital games in the subjects of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM). • Student as video gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot test applied in a school attended by secondary school students with hearing problems). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of a questionnaire, complemented by observation of the classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Games include multisensory settings, capable of engaging the player in a meaningful experience. • Concerning their gaming experience, more than 88% of students found gamification interesting. Only 5% expressed an unfavourable opinion about this practice. Learning engagement in STEM subjects, due to gamification practices, increased by about 78%. • The questionnaire proved that students felt rewarded after the gamified experience and were more interested in the act of learning. • Providing options in video games that allow customisation favours involvement.
	Between level up and game over: A systematic literature review of gamification in education	Manzano-León et al.	2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All levels of education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examine the existing evidence regarding the impact of educational gamification on student motivation and school performance in the last five years. • Student as video gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic Review principles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The author does not describe methods for measuring engagement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The most studied variables are motivation, school performance and engagement, followed by participation, fun and cognitive variables. • Extrinsic motivation corresponds to the most encouraged in educational gamification, consisting of, for example, the use of virtual medals. • Nevertheless, educational games allow for effective learning and intrinsically motivated

								<p>engagement. It helps teaching and reinforcing curricula content in an attractive way.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mechanics, graphics and interactivity in educational video games are the main sources of engagement and motivation. • It is important to pay more attention to the process involved in designing serious video games, as a poorly designed game negatively affects students' intrinsic motivation.
	Modelling the Player and Avatar Attachment based on Student's Engagement and Attention in Educational Games	Mohd Tuah et al.	2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-specified. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To propose a new player-avatar relationship model, based on student engagement and attention dedicated to the experience of playing serious video games. • Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the PLAVA model – Player Avatar Attachment and evaluation of this resource through interviews with experts in the field of design. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authors advocate that mixed methods should be used rather than the single use of questionnaires in order to measure learning engagement generated by serious video games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avatars are sources of engagement in serious video games as a result of a unification process between the graphic representation of the characters and the player. The identification of the latter with the avatar is essential for their immersion in the video game. • It is necessary to employ mixed methods to accurately determine the potential of avatars in DGBL – Digital Game-based Learning – contexts.
	Designing Engaging Games for Education: A Systematic Literature Review on Game Motivators and Design Principles	Laine, & Lindberg.	2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-specified. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To undertake a systematic review, aimed at creating a taxonomy containing 56 elements that favour motivation in games, framed in 14 classes, and designing a taxonomy of 54 principles for video game design. • Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of a method for conducting systematic reviews, proposed by Kitchenham and Charters (2007). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The authors do not describe or propose methods for measuring student engagement generated by serious video games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement, especially when based on intrinsic motivation, is essential for the success of pedagogical interventions. • Elements such as the player's control over the game and its narrative's relevance, especially when combined with an epic element, are important motivators. • Research on the design of serious video games lack a rigorous description of game elements that enhance student engagement and motivation. • Designing educational video games is a field of research rich in terms of the scientific discoveries already made and the paths that

								still need to be taken by teachers and researchers.
Testing the usability of digital educational games for encouraging smoking cessation	Guo et al.	2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vocational high-school students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To assess the effect of digital educational games on students' intention to quit smoking through an observational design. Three determinants of video game-generated engagement were measured: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and perceived satisfaction. Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability assessments were performed using a structured questionnaire and usability-testing software. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perceived ease of use, usefulness, and satisfaction – the three determinants of engagement – were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ('strongly disagree') to 5 ('strongly agree'). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educational video games designed to enhance both knowledge-building and motivation can provide for easy to use, useful and satisfactory learning experiences. To deliver a message successfully, one should resort to interactive learning environments such as the ones represented in video games. Positive changes in behavioural intentions among student smokers were reported. Behavioural intention can engender behavioural change. Engagement was seen as more significant than the participants' background in terms of the acquisition of new attitudes towards smoking. Students' background characteristics were not associated with perceived ease of use, usefulness, or satisfaction. Interactive digital content can be helpful for future smoking cessation, as it rewards students with a sense of relevance. Perceived usefulness of learning about the barriers, processes, and strategies related to smoking cessation favour the transformation of the experience engendered by smoking cessation-related educational video games into meaningful behavioural change. 	
Serious gaming for climate adaptation—assessing the potential and challenges of a digital serious game for urban climate adaptation	Neset et al.	2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students in High Education between 15 and 19 years old. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present the design and evaluation of <i>The Climate Adaptation</i>, a serious video game aimed at immersing high school students, practitioners and politicians in experiences that illustrate the impact of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Five gaming events were organized, with a moderator playing the role-playing game on a screen, except for two sessions where the students tested the game in pairs before providing feedback. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A questionnaire was administered to students, in order to ascertain their views on the overall theme of climate adaptation, game content, game functionality, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> While educational video games related to climate change can exert a positive influence on students' attitudes towards this theme, one must raise questions concerning the possible obstacles emerging from using video games for educational purposes: the importance of the terminology used, the need to think the available modes through – single player or role-play – as well as the complexity of the feedback system. 	

					climate adaptation measures, while educating them on selected Agenda 2030 goals.	Experts and politicians were invited to partake in the role-playing activities centred on the video game.	assessment and learning experience.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication, inclusivity and video games' legitimacy as to their ability to tackle important global issues should, likewise, be problematized in the process of developing an engaging serious video game and reflecting on its effectiveness. • The collected data reflected that the game sparked a high degree of interest in learning more about climate adaptation, succeeding in contextualizing and elucidating an important socio-scientific issue. Furthermore, students agreed that knowledge-building occurred when playing the game, despite having reported a high level of prior knowledge on the subject.
	Mobile games for negotiated-play and decision-making in health literacy	Themistokleous et al.	2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High school students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To present a mobile game for promoting health knowledge in secondary education. • Students as gamers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A case study was performed, in which students are interviewed about their representations regarding a mobile game about health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of interviews. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programmers, teachers and designers of serious video games should work together so as to align the graphic and sound dimension with the pedagogical goals students are expected to fulfil, and the theme of the video game. Thus, they ensure that the use of video games is consistent with pedagogical activities, improving students' experience of playing and their conscious engagement. • If there is a multiplayer mode in the video game, it paves the way to the activation of collective metacognitive processes, conscious engagement and the joint planning of strategies leading to problem solving.
	A guide for game-design-based gamification	Gallego-Durán et al.	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study is targeted at educators and researchers. The practices it depicts are applicable to all 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To present a rubric for educators and researchers to acquire initial experience in gamification, comprising ten characteristics. It is aimed at analysing existing games or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of a rubric that measures game-design-based gamification, according to 10 criteria, attaching to each one a score from 0 to 20 points. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement is measured indirectly in all characteristics, except for challenge, where the theory of the channel of flow is referred, and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The rubric described in the article holds potential to effectively create an engaging and effective game design, by analysing its strengths and weaknesses, while highlighting areas for improvement. • Given its artistic dimension, the development of the rubric was based on previous

				levels of education.	gamified activities to better understand their strengths and weaknesses and facilitate the process of designing or improving gamified learning experiences.		emotional entailment, where the connection with learning engagement or flow is more evident. This is due to the common association of engagement to positive emotions triggered by immersive learning experiences. All characteristics are measured on a scale from 0 to 2 points.	experience from authors and works from experts. As a result, the criteria it presents is flexible and open to multiple interpretations. This may represent both a strength and a weakness: it does not allow for objective assessments, but considers emotions and player experiences, which is important for creating designs aimed at providing meaningful learning. Another limitation pertains to the simplistic nature of this rubric, which may not fulfil experienced practitioners' expectations.
	Main gamification concepts: A systematic mapping study	Rodrigues, Oliveira, & Rodrigues	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-specified. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To conduct an analysis of the literature covering 50 papers from 2011 to 2016, using Leximancer software, to identify the main themes and concepts covered by gamification papers. The research question was: "What guidelines may provide to future research, the key themes and concepts found in published scientific papers on gamification?". 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative analysis using Leximancer tool. The steps followed were: Definition of a Research Question, Searches in Google Scholar, Selection and download of the 50 more relevant indexed papers, Extraction of the all the data in these papers, Upload of the Excel spreadsheet in Leximancer, Textual and content analysis, Selection of the most relevant themes and concepts on gamification and Generation of a 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of the Leximancer tool. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification corresponds to technology with games' features, resulting in an attractive way of increasing users' will and intention to engage with it. • Gamification is deeply intertwined with the concepts of work, engagement, context, activity, users, systems, use, process, elements, applications, and mechanics concepts. Such connection appears frequently in the sections 'Abstract', 'Future research' and 'Conclusions' in gamification papers. • Both points and meaning on their own and the combination increase intrinsic motivation in equal measure. In papers' conclusions, it is suggested that more efforts should be invested in measuring the attitudes toward the gamified activities as well as intentions to partake in those activities.

						Systematic Concept Map.		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As video games, social games are growing in popularity and incorporation in educational settings. Gamification is a new concept seeking to use elements from video games and social games in non-game applications.
Exploring the digital game-based elements in mathematics education: A meta-analysis review	Harikrishnan et al.	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Non-specified. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To reflect critically on the existing empirical studies of digital game-based learning courseware in the domain of Mathematics. Ultimately, the paper aims at identifying effective game-based elements to customize an engaging learning courseware. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Systematic review (meta-analysis) describing empirical studies (quasi-experimental) centred on a computer-based-game in Mathematical educational setting, integrating constructivism theory and game-based elements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The authors do not describe or propose methods for assessing engagement generated by serious video games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Applying digital game-based approaches brings a positive effect to learners' experiences. The outcome element – a game-based indicator of significant and essential apprenticeships learners would have acquired at the end of a given course – is the most recurrent element in papers, as it helps them distinguish and achieving learning goals more easily. This exerts a positive impact both on performance and engagement. In a subsequent place comes problem-solving, in correlation with interaction, since it enables learners to collaboratively identify problems and work out strategies to solve them, thus developing higher-order thinking skills. In third place come play, fun and interaction, behavioural-related elements, which foster intense and passionate involvement in learners to adapt games as a form of learning material and to construct new knowledge. Moreover, it can enhance their creativity, memory and geometry performances. Clear instructions and graphical animations help learners find games easier to play and less frustrating. This is conducive to higher levels of engagement. Opportunities for replaying a serious game are also important for engaging students in effective learning. When students experience multiple times the representation element in a game – the fantasy story – they can 	

								<p>discover new meanings in it, while improving their contextual understanding of the game.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenge and conflict improve the learners' potential to engage in game playing. In last place come rules, emotion and multitasking, which trigger ego gratification emotions, essential to derive fulfilment from serious games in a constrained way: rules prevent players from deviating from game goals and playing in an excessively passionate matter. In order words, they can avoid attaching their self-worth to their in-game performance.
	Initial validation of the MAKE framework: A comprehensive instrument for evaluating the efficacy of game-based learning and gamification in adolescent sexual health literacy	Haruna et al.	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secondary school students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To report on the creation and evaluation of a framework for assessing the efficacy of games in teaching sexual health behaviours to secondary school learners in low resource settings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The framework built – MAKE – was initially validated by comparing data from the results of questionnaires applied to a control and experiment group. The data collected was subjected to factor analysis test and the scale reliability measured by applying Cronbach's alpha. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation and engagement (emotional and cognitive) were assessed through the administration of questionnaires to a control and experiment group. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivation constructs (ARCS) were proven valid for measuring the efficacy of different teaching methods. The attitudinal dimension should be considered in evaluating teaching methods, due to its strong connection with human behaviour. The positive or negative feelings experienced by participants determine whether they will succeed in the acquisition of responsible sexual health behaviour. In the MAKE scale, attitudinal constructs were divided into cognitive and affective items. Behavioural attitudes were disregarded because their measurement requires a longitudinal study. Initial validation of the engagement instruments confirmed that their items were satisfactory for examining teaching methods, having met the required standards for validity and reliability. This study validates the MAKE framework as an efficient instrument for assessing the efficacy of teaching methods in interactive teaching environments that intend to support

								students' knowledge acquisition and its transposition into a real-world setting.
	A framework for climate change engagement through video games	Ouariachi et al.	2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students aged from 12 to 18 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To present a set of game attributes which enhance the cognitive, emotional and behavioural engagement of players and lay the foundation for future research. By analysing experts and teenagers' perspectives, the authors have developed a framework for climate change engagement through serious games. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of a qualitative, interpretative approach to data collection and analysis. Grounded theory was derived from semi-structured interviews with key experts and validated through a group discussion with teenagers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experts were interviewed on the projects they have implemented concerning climate change and the attributes of a serious game essential to cognitive, emotional and behavioural engagement. Likewise, teenagers were asked to imagine they were game designers and suggest attributes that would engage players in learning about climate change. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the proposed framework, serious games focused on climate change should be: achievable, challenging, concrete, credible, efficacy-enhancing (empowering and fulfilling), centred on experiential learning, feedback-oriented, fun, identity-driven, aimed at levelling up, meaningful, narrative driven, reward-driven, stimulating and social. This framework – comprised of three dimensions (cognitive, emotional and behavioural), and 15 attributes was designed to engage digital natives. The perceptions of experts converged with those of the students interviewed. The line separating the different variables is hard to establish as they can be simultaneously cognitive, emotional and behavioural. Constructivism is valued by the experts and students. Their opinions stressed the importance of a multi-outcome system, in which the learning experience is student-centred and based on the exchange of different perspectives, giving rise to different actions and a fuller understanding of the content conveyed by the game. Notwithstanding, there are limitations, namely the heavy focus on the opinions of a specific group of researchers. To achieve a higher degree of legitimacy, more theoretical and empirical research needs to be conducted.